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DAMAGE VISUAL INDICATION SYSTEM FOR POLYMER COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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PROJECTS

#ICCM22

Fabric, impregnated with the mixture:

-Leuco dye
-Colour developer

50 °C

75 °C

100 °C

125 °C

150 °C

200 °C

Deformation vs. applied force until the rupture of the microcapsule

Nanoindentation curve in the small deformation regime

RESULTS

- Microcapsules are thermal stable till 350 °C.
- Microcapsules have ability to change colour till 150 °C.
- Diameter $D1 \approx 7 \mu\text{m}$ and $D2 \approx 2 \mu\text{m}$.
- Shell thickness for both types of m/c is $h \approx 0.10 \mu\text{m}$.
- Elastic modulus of microcapsule shell material $1.7 \text{ was } \pm 0.2 \text{ GPa}$.

Colour response vs. different concentration of microcapsules

warranty: adhesion and damage indication ability is observed at least during 6 years of storage at room conditions

DVIS with different colour microcapsules; colour response vs. applied load

Typical visual response curve vs. time after applied load

